

IMPROVING THE ADHERENCE OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS SUFFERERS WITH PHARMACY CARE: A SCIENTIFIC ASSESSMENT OF RANDOMIZED MANAGED TRIALS

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Abstract: Background: Oral medication for patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus plays an important role in diabetes care and is associated with high levels of self-care and self-management behavior. Complications and increased mortality. Barriers to adherence can include complex treatment regimens, often associated with multiple long-term therapies, side effects from medications, and inadequate, incomprehensible, or confusing information or instructions from the healthcare provider. Multidisciplinary approaches can support successful adherence and enable more effective management of diabetes care.

The focus of diabetes care can be the involvement of a pharmacist. The aim was to analyze the effectiveness of pharmaceutical interventions to improve adherence to therapy in type 2 diabetes mellitus. Methods: A systematic review of randomized controlled trials. Study quality was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias Tool. Results: Six publications were included out of 491 results.

Two studies investigating primarily educational interventions showed a significant improvement in therapy adherence. In addition, the quality of the included studies was poor. Conclusion: Although pharmaceutical interventions could potentially improve medication adherence in type 2 diabetes mellitus, high-quality studies are needed to assess their effectiveness.

Keywords: Oral medication, healthcare provider, type 2 diabetes mellitus.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background

Oral medication for patients with kind two diabetes plays a very important role in polygenic disorder care and is related to a high level self-care behavior and self-management [1]. However, poor adherence to diabetes treatment is common that causes severe health complications and increased mortality [2-4]. this can be mirrored as an example

by a rise within the risk of vessel diseases, neuropathy, retinopathy, kidney disease and hospitalization rates [3,5,6].

Barriers to adherence might encompass complicated treatment regimens often at the side of long-run multi-therapies, side effects because of the medication furthermore as insufficient, in- accessible or confusing info or directions provided by the health care provider.

Further boundaries hard adherence can also be associated with socioeco- nomic issues, reminiscence impairment, mental well- being and private beliefs [5,7,8].

Multidisciplinary processes can help adherence achievement and might permit a extra powerful control of diabetes care. Several fashions for diabetes care had been advanced and evaluated [9]. One technique in diabetes care may be the involvement of a pharmacist, especially because the position of a pharmacist has modified withinside the final decades. As the schooling of pharmacists and their responsibilities consist of extra than just the producing and management of medicinal products, incorporating pharmacists withinside the direct care of diabetic sufferers ought to make contributions to supporting sufferers attain most beneficial adherence [10-13]. The duties of pharmacists contain as an example the long-term supervision, patient education activities, the attention of medication-associated issues (e.g. drug interactions) and of affected person desires as nicely as the optimization of the medicinal remedy and adherence. Studies have proven that pharmacist interventions undoubtedly have an effect on fitness results and affected person satisfaction, that are important signs for exceptional of fitness care and a key component for medicinal drug adherence [11].

A preceding systematic evaluation tested the outcomes of pharmacist interventions that enhance adherence to oral antidiabetic medicines for kind 2 diabetes mellitus displaying a advantageous impact on adherence [14]. However, even though a look for educational, behavioral, affective or provider-centered techniques is defined the furnished seek method is confined to sure seek phrases which would possibly result in a non-identity of applicable publications. Further, the recognized research protected withinside the evaluation is simply defined with appreciate to the look at characteristics, forms of interventions and look at results, but, they're now no longer systematically assessed for exceptional which impedes the vast and concluding appraisal of the respective interventions. Moreover, the evaluation protected cohort research further to randomized managed trials aiming to offer exhaustive and generalizable results. Nevertheless, the attention of non-randomized trials does now no longer seem to enhance the cost of the evaluation with appreciate to in addition final results measures or longer follow-ups. Therefore, it changed into sought to carry out a scientific evaluation on randomized managed trials studying the effectiveness of adherence- improving interventions regarding pharmacists for oral medicinal drug in kind 2 diabetes mellitus.

2. METHODS

Literature seek and choice criteria

A systematic look for applicable courses become con- ducted in bibliographic databases (Medline through EMBASE, EMBASE through EMBASE, CENTRAL through Cochrane Library) in March, 2013. A seek method for every database become advanced the usage of scientific difficulty headings and key phrases for adherence, pharmacist interventions and sort 2 dia- betes mellitus. The complete seek techniques are supplied in Additional report 1. Randomized managed/cluster- randomized managed trials as complete-textual content courses investigating pharmacist interventions wherein a pharmacist is in- volved withinside the provision of the intervention to enhance adherence, described because the diploma to which a affected person follows the scientific prescription in phrases of interval and dose of a dosing regimen [15], to oral medicinal drug in kind 2 diabetes mellitus had been eligible for inclusion. If the kind 2 diabetes mellitus medicinal drug couldn't be virtually classi- fied as oral medicinal drug (e.g. metformin, alpha-glucosidase inhibitors, thiazolidinediones) the have a look at become excluded. Moreover, the tested populace needed to include person patients (≥ 18 years) and adherence to the oral medicinal drug in kind 2 diabetes mellitus needed to be measured. No limitation concerning the language or ebook 12 months of the research become made.

Study selection

Study selection: Two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts of the identified publications according to predefined criteria. Upon receipt of the full texts of potentially relevant publications, these were reviewed by two independent reviewers and found suitable for further analysis. If discrepancies regarding study inclusion could not be resolved through discussion, a third reviewer was consulted.

Data extraction

The results and study characteristics of each included study were then extracted and checked for accuracy and completeness by a second reviewer. Standardized tables were used for this. These contained information on the first author, the year of publication, the type of study, the country and location of the study, the size of the study population, age and gender, as well as the content and duration of the intervention and the control intervention, the definition of adherence, the adherence measures and the Adherence rate at baseline and at last follow-up. Risk of bias The risk of bias in the included studies was assessed by two independent reviewers according to predefined criteria based on the Cochrane

Risk of bias

However, the criteria for blinding participants and staff were not applicable. For interventions to improve adherence, participants and staff delivering the intervention cannot be blinded by the nature of the interventions. Therefore, the relevant criteria were not applied. Consequently, the criteria implemented to assess the methodological quality of the included studies consisted of questions on random sequence generation, attribution obfuscation, blinding of outcome assessment, intention-to-treat analysis, selective reporting, and others.

If discrepancies regarding the quality assessment could not be clarified through discussion, a third assessor was consulted. We have chosen to rate each element of risk of bias only as 'yes' and 'no' rather than 'unclear' as recent research suggests. suggests that the classification as “unclear” “becomes the default for assessing the risk of bias (RoB) in relation to reliability” [17]. In addition, it could be shown that there is a “significant difference in the effect sizes [...] in the case of high or unclear risk of bias and those with a low risk of bias” [18].

3. RESULTS

The literature search resulted in a total of 491 articles (Figure 1). After screening titles and abstracts, 23 publications were considered potentially relevant for further screening [9,19-40]. Two of these publications could not be obtained and were therefore excluded. Eight studies were excluded mainly because adherence was not measured.

Four studies didn't have associate intervention at intervals that a caregiver was actively involved within the availability of adherence-enhancing ways that for oral type 2 DM medication. In one study the examined study population weren't adults (≥18 years), in one study the kind a pair of DM medication wasn't associate oral medication and one study wasn't a irregular con- trolled trial. In total, six publications met the selection criteria and were capsule for a lot of analysis [9,19-23].

The enclosed studies showed qualitative deficits in terms of risk of bias (Table 1). In most studies the allo-ion sequence was not sufficiently generated (n = 4) in addition as hid (n = five), most likely inflicting a range bias. Further, the

blazing of outcome assessment wasn't reportable in 5 of the capsule studies associate degreeed associate ana- lysis per intention-to-treat was painted in 1/2 the enclosed studies. In a pair of studies a potential risk for selective news and various sources of bias could also be identified. These are additional portrayed at intervals the subsequent for each study once describing the results.

Among the included irregular-controlled trials one study was a cluster-randomized controlled trial within that the collaborating pharmacists were arbitrarily assigned to the intervention or management cluster [9]. The investigated interventions consisted of educational interventions supporting the correct medication use in addition as reminders and message interventions, provided by pharmacists in cooperation with the treating doctor in various settings and countries, as an example patient health care facilities, pharmacies and hospital settings (Table 2).

In 5 research [9,19-21,23] instructional interventions (e.g. via way of means of telecall smartphone or as group activities) addressing subjects consisting of disease, remedy, diet, and way of life change had been evaluated. In 3 of those research instructional interventions had been supplied further to social offerings and vitamins session in addition to re- minders approximately annual eye and foot examinations, individual follow-up attendances, scheduled conferences with a pharmacist and/or typical care [9,20,21]. One takes a look at investigated the implementation of a Diabetes Care Plan further to weekly in-man or woman or telecall smartphone conferences and month-to-month follow-up telecall smartphone calls [22]. Most interventions had been as compared with typical care [9,21-23] while Adepu et al. and Grant et al. used a cut-down provision of educational interventions because the comparator [19,20]. The period and durations of the interventions various throughout all research (from 3 to 36 months and from each 30 days to each 6 months).

In 4 of the research adherence become described as the percentage of medicine taken [9,21-23], in a single take a look at the common extrade in adherence and in a single take a look at the common extrade of the quantity of neglected remedy withinside the final 7 days had been measured [19,20]. Self-suggested adherence become utilized in nearly all research to degree adherence [9,19-21,23]. The prescription top off rate [9], the periodicity of prescription pickups [21] had been used further in research and tablet rely become used to degree adherence via way of means of Phumipamorn [23]. Detailed information on country, setting, populace size in addition to age and intercourse may be observed in Table 2.

Table 1: Risk of bias of included trials

Study	Adepu (2010) [19]	Grant (2003) [20]	Mehuys (2011) [9]	Obreli-Neto (2011) [21]	Odegard (2005) [22]	Phumipamorn (2008) [23]
Random generation of allocation sequence	-	-	+	-	-	+
Allocation concealment	-	-	+	-	-	-
Blinding of outcome assessment	-	-	-	+	-	-
Analysis according to intention-to-treat	-	-	+	+	+	-
Selective reporting	-	-	+	-	+	-
Other sources of bias	+	-	+	-	-	-

+ fulfilled, - not fulfilled.

A trend towards pharmaceutical intervention to improve adherence in type 2 diabetes mellitus was reported in all studies, but only the studies by Odegard et al. showed a statistically significant effect. ($p=0.003$) and Phumipamorn et al ($p=0.004$) (Table 2) [9,19-23]. Odegard et al. studied a diabetes care plan combined with weekly face-to-face or telephone meetings and monthly pharmacist telephone follow-up visits compared to usual care [22]. They found that adherence was significantly higher in the intervention group than in the control group; However, adherence rates have not been reported [22] Phumipamorn et al. showed that providing scheduled meetings with a pharmacist in conjunction with the doctor's appointment significantly increased adherence to therapy compared to usual care. Adepu et al. three months) compared to just one training session (in the third month) tended to improve adherence [19]. However, the adherence between the intervention and control groups at the start of the study differed significantly, even though the study was a randomized controlled trial. test. It was not reported whether differences at baseline were adjusted for in their analysis. Educational telephone interviews, in addition to social services and nutritional counseling offered and arranged by a pharmacist identified by Grant et al. reduced the number of forgotten medications, but the control group, which only received the telephone interviews, showed almost perfect adherence in both groups even in the final measurement [20]. In the cluster-randomized study by Mehuys et al. Greater antidiabetic medication adherence was reported in the intervention group that

received education and reminders of annual eye and foot exams compared to regular treatment. Baseline adherence of the intervention and control groups was not reported. In addition, the possibility of group effects and the significance of the study results were not described. In addition, all patients with >100% adherence were excluded from the analysis in this study [9]. Usual care complemented by a pharmaceutical care intervention consisting of individual follow-up attendances and instructive cluster activities was compared to usual care by Obreli-Neto et al. and perceived to improve adherence, however no statistically vital impact was delineated [21,23].

4. DISCUSSION

The performed systematic review searched and analyzed randomized controlled trials on apothecary interventions for patients taking oral sort two polygenic disorder medication with relation to adherence. altogether six enclosed studies the effect direction was in favor of the pharmacist interventions on up adherence to medicament medication. Overall, of the six included studies 2 studies showed a statistically vital impact of a polygenic disorder Care set up combined with weekly in-person and/or phone-phone conferences and monthly follow-up telephone calls provided by apothecary and of a pharmaceutical care intervention consisting of the supply of regular meetings with a pharmacist aboard with the physician's appointment compared with usual care [22,23].

However, the enclosed studies contain in elements hetero- geneous interventions additionally as totally different strategies to define, to operationalize and to live adherence solely granting a comparison to a restricted extent. In 5 studies [9,19-21,23] instructional interventions (e.g. by telephone or as cluster activities) addressing topics admire disease, medication, diet, and style modification were evaluated. In 3 of those studies instructional interventions were provided additionally to social services and nutrition consultation additionally as reminders regarding annual eye and foot examinations, individual follow-up attendances, regular conferences with a apothecary and/ or usual care [9,20,21]. Most interventions were com- pared with usual care [9,21-23] whereas Adepu et al. and Grant et al. used a cut-down provision of educational interventions because the comparator [19,20]. In addition, as mentioned, self-reported adherence as well as the prescription refill rate, the regularity of prescrip- tion pickups and pill count were primarily enforced because the adherence live within the enclosed studies. Al- tho' these represent adherence measures unremarkably implemented, they could be subjected to overestimation of adherence [41,42].

Table 2: Study results

Author, Year	Adepu (2010) [19]	Grant (2003) [20]	Mehuys (2011) [9]	Obreli-Neto (2011) [21]	Odegard (2005) [22]	Phumipamorn (2008) [23]
Study type	RCT	RCT	Cluster-RCT	RCT	RCT	RCT
Country/ Setting	South India/Medicine Outpatient Department Tertiary care teaching hospital	USA/Academically affiliated community health center	Belgium/Community pharmacies	Brazil/Public Primary Health Care Unit	USA/University of Washington Medicine Clinics	Thailand/Community Hospital
Population (IG/CG)	n = 227	62/58	153/135	97/97	39/27	63/67
Age (IG/CG)	>57	64 ± 12/69 ± 10	62 (45-79)/63 (40-84)	65 ± 5.8/65 ± 5.7	52 ± 11.6/52 ± 10.4	52 ± 11.15/56 ± 13.67
Sex (IG/CG)	49% female	55%/69% female	54%/51% male	63%/62% female	48%/48% female	92%/76% female
Intervention	Education (Baseline, every 30 days for a period of 3 months)	Educational telephone interview + social services/nutrition consultation (Baseline, 3 months)	Education & Reminders about annual eye and foot examinations (Baseline, at each prescription refill visit for a period of 6 months)	Usual care + individual follow-up attendances & educative group activities (every 6 months for period of 36 months)	Diabetes care plan DCP) & Weekly in person/telephone meetings & monthly follow-up phone calls (6-month intervention, follow-up at month 6 and 12)	Usual care & 4 scheduled meetings with a pharmacist (every 2 months) & education
Control	Education (month 3)	Educational telephone interview	Usual care	Usual care	Usual care	Usual care
Definition adherence	Average change in adherence (0-4 scale)	Amount of missed medication in the last 7 days (change from baseline)	Proportion of doses taken (%)	Proportion of doses taken (%)	Proportion of missed doses (%)	Proportion of doses taken (%)
Adherence measure	Self-reported adherence	Self-reported adherence	Prescription refill rate & self-reported adherence	Self-reported adherence & periodicity of prescription pickup	Self-reported adherence	Pill count
Adherence (IG/CG)						
Baseline	0.73/1.11	6.7/6.9	NR	51/49 53/53	56/35	82/87
Final (%)	0.88/0.67 p = NR	0.1/0.1 (change from baseline) p = 0.8	99.7/94.7 (prescription refill rate) p = NR 61/62 (self-reported adherence) p = NR	84/44 (self-reported adherence) 84/43 (periodicity of prescription pickup) p = NR	IG < CG p = 0.003	89/85 p = 0.004

NR = Not reported, IG = intervention group, CG = control group.

Furthermore, besides changes in adherence rates all included studies measured additionally relevant clinical outcomes appreciate blood sugar and vital sign values as their reduction and maintenance are key aims in polygenic disease care to forestall attainable complications and to realize health gains in diabetic patients [34]. Statistically important changes in blood pressure and blood glucose levels were found in favor of the intervention teams receiving pharmaceutical care within the majority of the studies [9,19,21-23]. different relevant outcomes such as information and self-management as factors moving adherence were conjointly assessed. The involvement of a pill pusher contributed to AN improvement of information and self-care activities in 3 studies [9,19,23]. However, totally {different|completely different} instruments were used for the assessment and knowledge moreover as self-management values at the baseline and final assessment varied among and between the study teams among the studies. Moreover, the sample size wasn't adequately calculated in most of the studies or the sample size calculation was not rumored [9,19-22].

A attainable limitation is that pharmacists might individually differ within the method they supply their adherence-enhancing intervention. Additionally, they may show variations in distinguishing individual medication-related problems AND patient needs, the intensity of the pill pusher-patient contact moreover as in education and communication skills inflicting variances in outcomes. This issue has also been noted in different connected publications [43,44]. Moreover, a facet to be thought of is that the truth that pharmacists within their several health care systems, during which the studies were conducted, are otherwise integrated in the health care provision [45]. For instance, in some health care systems pharmacist care may be felt and integrated as an organized component in the management of diseases as in different health care systems. Aspects appreciate education, professionalization, recognition and compensation simply to mention some are essential influencing factors relating to the variations in pharmacy care [46,47]. The differences within the role of pill pushers in several countries contribute to the difficulty in examination the various pharmacist interventions. Hence, creating a generalized conclusion remains difficult, particularly against the background that the analyzed irregular controlled trials are conducted in various different countries with varied living circumstances and cultural backgrounds. we tend to couldn't choose in however way the results of our quality assessment are in line with the standard assessment by Omran et al. as their results are not represented in detail. additionally to the irregular controlled trials conjointly identified by Omran et al. our review known 3 any relevant randomized controlled trials. 2 studies by Al Mazroui et al. and Skaer et al. [34,39] which were included within the review by Omran et al. weren't enclosed in our review as they either failed to fulfill our inclusion criteria or were not accessible.

The influence of caregiver interventions in increasing adherence has been incontestable in many publications, showing that the results of our review are in line with those of alternative publications, however ever, in how way health outcomes, quality of life or cost-effectiveness are improved is ambiguous [10,11,14,44,48]. Thus, additional studies of top quality are required to assess important effectiveness of adherence-enhancing pharmacist interventions care, particularly against the background that the study quality of the enclosed trials during this review are deficient [14,49,50].

5. CONCLUSION

Our review shows the prevailing proof on the effectiveness of caregiver interventions to reinforce adherence in patients suffering sort a pair of diabetes. The outcomes of the analyzed studies indicate that pharmacists may have AN authoritative and important role within the respective health care system to boost adherence in patients taking oral type 2 polygenic disorder mellitus medication. However, the nonuniformity of study populations interventions, adherence measures and outcomes in the included studies prevents a comparison in addition as a generalization. Besides, our review points out the lack of randomized controlled trials of caregiver interventions in oral sort a pair of diabetes medication. Nevertheless, pharmacists ought to be further thought-about as AN integral part within the health care provision for type 2 diabetes mellitus care, particularly in terms of serving to patients to cut back non-adherence and thence to boost health outcomes in patients taking oral type 2 diabetes mellitus medication. Future randomized controlled trials should be looked for to supply comparable results of outcomes

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Authors' contributions

AMS: research question development, search strategy development, study selection, data analysis, interpretation of results, preparation of the manuscript. AN: research question development, search strategy development, study selection, interpretation of results, review of the manuscript. AM research question development, search strategy development, study selection, data analysis, interpretation of results, review of the manuscript. MN: research question development, search strategy development, review of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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REFERENCES

- [1] World Health Organisation (WHO): Adherence to Long-Term Therapies- Evidence for action. 2003.
- [2] Cramer JA, Okikawa J, Bellaire S, Clauson P: Compliance with inhaled insulin treatment using the AERx(registered trademark) iDMS insulin diabetes management system. *Diab Technol Ther* 2004, 6(6):800–807.
- [3] Vermeire EIJJ, Wens J, Van Royen P, Biot Y, Hearnshaw H, Lindenmeyer A: Interventions for improving adherence to treatment recommendations in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2005, (2):CD003638.
- [4] Ho PM, Rumsfeld JS, Masoudi FA, McClure DL, Plomondon ME, Steiner JF, Magid DJ: Effect of medication nonadherence on hospitalization and mortality among patients with diabetes mellitus. *Arch Intern Med* 2006, 166(17):1836–1841. PubMed PMID: 17000939. Epub 2006/09/27. eng.
- [5] Currie CJ, Peyrot M, Morgan CL, Poole CD, Jenkins-Jones S, Rubin RR, Burton CM, Evans M: The impact of treatment noncompliance on mortality in people with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2012, 35(6):1279–1284. PubMed PMID: 22511257. Pubmed Central PMCID: 3357221. Epub 2012/ 04/19. eng.
- [6] World Health Organisation (WHO): Definition, Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes Mellitus and Its Complications. Part 1: Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes Mellitus. 1999.
- [7] Nam S, Chesla C, Stotts NA, Kroon L, Janson SL: Barriers to diabetes management: patient and provider factors. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* 2011, 93(1):1–9. PubMed PMID: 21382643. Epub 2011/03/09. eng.
- [8] Odegard PS, Gray SL: Barriers to medication adherence in poorly controlled diabetes mellitus. *Diab Educ* 2008, 34(4):692–697.
- [9] Mehuys E, Van Bortel L, De Bolle L, Van Tongelen I, Annemans L, Remon JP, Giri M: Effectiveness of a community pharmacist intervention in diabetes care: a randomized controlled trial. *J Clin Pharm Ther* 2011, 36(5):602–613.
- [10] Lindenmeyer A, Hearnshaw H, Vermeire E, Van Royen P, Wens J, Biot Y: Interventions to improve adherence to medication in people with type 2 diabetes mellitus: a review of the literature on the role of pharmacists. *J Clin Pharm Ther* 2006, 31(5):409–419. PubMed PMID: 16958818. Epub 2006/ 09/09. eng.
- [11] Spinewine A, Fialova D, Byrne S: The role of the pharmacist in optimizing pharmacotherapy in older people. *Drugs Aging* 2012, 29(6):495–510. PubMed PMID: 22642783. Epub 2012/05/31. eng.
- [12] Hume AL, Kirwin J, Bieber HL, Couchenour RL, Hall DL, Kennedy AK, LaPointe NM, Burkhardt CD, Schilli K, Seaton T, Trujillo J, Wiggins B: Improving care transitions: current practice and future opportunities for pharmacists. *Pharmacotherapy* 2012, 32(11):e326–e337. PubMed PMID: 23108810. Epub 2012/10/31. eng.
- [13] World Health Organisation (WHO): The Role of the Pharmacist in the Health Care System; 1993.
- [14] Omran D, Guirguis LM, Simpson SH: Systematic review of pharmacist interventions to improve adherence to oral antidiabetic medications in people with type 2 diabetes. *Can J Diab* 2012, 36(5):292–299.
- [15] Cramer JA, Roy A, Burrell A, Fairchild CJ, Fuldeore MJ, Ollendorf DA, Wong PK: Medication compliance and persistence: terminology and definitions. *Value Health* 2008, 11(1):44–47.
- [16] Higgins JP, Altman DG, Gotzsche PC, Juni P, Moher D, Oxman AD, Savovic J, Schulz KF, Weeks L, Sterne JA, Cochrane Bias Methods Group, Cochrane Statistical Methods Group: The cochrane collaboration's tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ* 2011, 343:d5928. PubMed PMID: 22008217. Pubmed Central PMCID: 3196245.

- [17] Hartling L, Hamm MP, Milne A, Vandermeer B, Santaguida PL, Ansari M, Tsertsvadze A, Hempel S, Shekelle P, Dryden DM: Testing the risk of bias tool showed low reliability between individual reviewers and across consensus assessments of reviewer pairs. *J Clin Epidemiol* 2013, 66(9):973–981. PubMed PMID: 22981249. Epub 2012/09/18. eng.
- [18] Hartling L, Ospina M, Liang Y, Dryden DM, Hooton N, Seida JK, Klassen TP: Risk of bias versus quality assessment of randomised controlled trials: cross sectional study. *BMJ* 2009, 37(09):339. 2009-10-19 11.
- [19] Adepu R, Ari SM: Influence of structured patient education on therapeutic outcomes in diabetes and hypertensive patients. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res* 2010, 3(3):174–178.
- [20] Grant RW, Devita NG, Singer DE, Meigs JB: Improving adherence and reducing medication discrepancies in patients with diabetes. *Ann Pharmacother* 2003, 37(7–8):962–969.
- [21] Obreli-Neto PR, Guidoni CM, De Oliveira BA, Pilger D, Cruciol-Souza JM, Gaeti-Franco WP, Cuman RKN: Effect of a 36-month pharmaceutical care program on pharmacotherapy adherence in elderly diabetic and hypertensive patients. *Int J Clin Pharm* 2011, 33(4):642–649.
- [22] Odegard PS, Goo A, Hummel J, Williams KL, Gray SL: Caring for poorly controlled diabetes mellitus: a randomized pharmacist intervention. *Ann Pharmacother* 2005, 39(3):433–440.
- [23] Phumipamorn S, Pongwecharak J, Soorapan S, Pattharachayakul S: Effects of the pharmacist's input on glycaemic control and cardiovascular risks in Muslim diabetes. *Prim Care Diab* 2008, 2(1):31–37.
- [24] Heisler M, Hofer TP, Schmittiel JA, Selby JV, Klamerus ML, Bosworth HB, Bermann M, Kerr EA: Improving blood pressure control through a clinical pharmacist outreach program in patients with diabetes mellitus in 2 high-performing health systems: the adherence and intensification of medications cluster randomized, controlled pragmatic trial. *Circulation* 2012, 125(23):2863–2872. PubMed PMID: 22570370. Epub 2012/05/10. eng.
- [25] Bogner HR, Morales KH, de Vries HF, Cappola AR: Integrated management of type 2 diabetes mellitus and depression treatment to improve medication adherence: a randomized controlled trial. *Ann Fam Med* 2012, 10(1):15–22. PubMed PMID: 22230826. Pubmed Central PMCID: 3262455.
- [26] Chan CW, Siu SC, Wong CK, Lee VW: A pharmacist care program: positive impact on cardiac risk in patients with type 2 diabetes. *J Cardiovasc Pharmacol Ther* 2012, 17(1):57–64. PubMed PMID: 21335480.
- [27] Cohen LB, Taveira TH, Khatana SA, Dooley AG, Pirraglia PA, Wu WC: Pharmacist-led shared medical appointments for multiple cardiovascular risk reduction in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Diab Educ* 2011, 37(6):801–812. PubMed PMID: 22021025. Epub 2011/10/25. eng.
- [28] Farmer A, Hardeman W, Hughes D, Prevost A, Kim Y, Craven A, Oke J, Boase S, Selwood M, Kellar I, Graffy J, Griffin S, Sutton S, Kinmonth AL: An explanatory randomised controlled trial of a nurse-led, consultation-based intervention to support patients with adherence to taking glucose lowering medication for type 2 diabetes. *BMC Fam Pract* 2012, 13(1):1–9. English.
- [29] Iram M, Pais N, Rani S: Impact Of Patient Counseling And Education Of Diabetic Patients In Improving Their Quality Of Life 2010. ; 2010:18–22.
- [30] Jacobs M, Sherry PS, Taylor LM, Amato M, Tataronis GR, Cushing G: Pharmacist Assisted Medication Program Enhancing the Regulation of Diabetes (PAMPERED) study. *J Am Pharm Assoc* 2012, 52(5):613–621. PubMed PMID: 23023841. Epub 2012/10/02. eng.
- [31] Jarab AS, Alqudah SG, Mukattash TL, Shattat G, Al-Qirim T: Randomized controlled trial of clinical pharmacy management of patients with type 2 diabetes in an outpatient diabetes clinic in Jordan. *J Manag Care Pharm* 2012, 18(7):516–526.
- [32] Planas LG, Crosby KM, Mitchell KD, Farmer KC: Evaluation of a hypertension medication therapy management program in patients with diabetes. *JAPhA* 2009, 49(2):164–170.
- [33] Ramanath KVYLS: Impact of clinical pharmacist provided patient education on QOL outcome in type II diabetes mellitus in rural population. *Asian J Pharma Clin Res* 2011, 4(4):15–20.

- [34] Al Mazroui NR, Kamal MM, Ghabash NM, Yacout TA, Kole PL, McElnay JC: Influence of pharmaceutical care on health outcomes in patients with Type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Br J Clin Pharmacol* 2009, 67(5):547–557.
- [35] Clifford RM, Batty KT, Davis TME, Davis W, Stein G, Stewart G, Plumridge RJ: A randomised controlled trial of a pharmaceutical care programme in high-risk diabetic patients in an outpatient clinic. *Int J Pharm Pract* 2002, 10(2):85–89.
- [36] Farsaei S, Sabzghabae AM, Zargarzadeh AH, Amini M: Effect of pharmacist-led patient education on glycaemic control of type 2 diabetics: a randomized controlled trial. *J Res Med Sci* 2011, 16(1):43–49.
- [37] Kirwin JL, Cunningham RJ, Sequist TD: Pharmacist recommendations to improve the quality of diabetes care: a randomized controlled trial. *J Manag Care Pharm* 2010, 16(2):104–113.
- [38] Krass I, Armour CL, Mitchell B, Brilliant M, Denaar R, Hughes J, Lau P, Peterson G, Stewart K, Taylor S, Wilkinson J: The pharmacy diabetes care program: assessment of a community pharmacy diabetes service model in Australia. *Diabet Med* 2007, 24(6):677–683.
- [39] Skaer TL, Sclar DA, Markowski DJ, Won JKH: Effect of value-added utilities on prescription refill compliance and Medicaid health care expenditures – a study of patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. *J Clin Pharm Ther* 1993, 18(4):295–299.
- [40] Suppavitiporn S, Chindavijak B, Onsanit S: Effect of diabetes drug counseling by pharmacist, diabetic disease booklet and special medication containers on glycaemic control of type 2 diabetes mellitus: a randomized controlled trial. *J Med Assoc Thai* 2005, 88(Suppl 4):S134–S141.
- [41] Jerant A, DiMatteo R, Arnsten J, Moore-Hill M, Franks P: Self-report adherence measures in chronic illness: retest reliability and predictive validity. *Med Care* 2008, 46(11):1134–1139. PubMed PMID: 18953223. Epub 2008/10/28. eng.
- [42] Gonzalez JS, Schneider HE, Wexler DJ, Psaros C, Delahanty LM, Cagliero E, Safren SA: Validity of medication adherence self-reports in adults with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2013, 36(4):831–837.
- [43] Patterson SM, Hughes C, Kerse N, Cardwell CR, Bradley MC: Interventions to improve the appropriate use of polypharmacy for older people. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2012, 5:CD008165. PubMed PMID: 22592727. Epub 2012/ 05/18. eng.
- [44] Ahmad A, Hugtenburg J, Welschen LM, Dekker JM, Nijpels G: Effect of medication review and cognitive behaviour treatment by community pharmacists of patients discharged from the hospital on drug related problems and compliance: design of a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Public Health* 2010, 10:133.
- [45] Tonna APSD, McCaig D: An international overview of some pharmacist prescribing models. *J Malta Coll Pharm Pract* 2008, (Issue 14):20–26.
- [46] Anderson S: The state of the world's pharmacy: a portrait of the pharmacy profession. *J Interprof Care* 2002, 16(4):391–404. PubMed PMID: 12487847. Epub 2002/12/19. eng.
- [47] Lutz EMRJ, Mattingly J, Reed BN: Pharmacy practice around the world. *J Am Pharm Assoc* 2009, 49(1):4–10.
- [48] Schnipper JL, Kirwin JL, Cotugno MC, Wahlstrom SA, Brown BA, Tarvin E, Kachalia A, Horng M, Roy CL, McKean SC, Bates DW: Role of pharmacist counseling in preventing adverse drug events after hospitalization. *Arch Intern Med* 2006, 166(5):565–571.
- [49] Melchioris A, Correr C, Venson R, Pontarolo R: An analysis of quality of systematic reviews on pharmacist health interventions. *Int J Clin Pharm* 2012, 34(1):32–42. English.
- [50] Royal S, Smeaton L, Avery AJ, Hurwitz B, Sheikh A: Interventions in primary care to reduce medication related adverse events and hospital admissions: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Qual Saf Health Care* 2006, 15(1):23–31. PubMed PMID: 16456206. Pubmed Central PMCID: 2563996. Epub 2006/02/04. eng.